

Yorùbá Ethical Values in Àdìtù Olódùmarè: A Philosophical Appraisal

Author Details: Aladesanmi Omobola Agnes Ph.d

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages Ekiti State University, Ado- Ekiti. Ekiti State Nigeria.

Abstract:

“Moral” as in relationship with “Ethics” deals with what relates to what is right and wrong in human behavior. It is what considered being right and good by most people; agreeing with a standard of right behavior. Moral can also mean a lesson from a story or an experience. Moral and ethics can be used interchangeably; and ethics as a branch of philosophy is a reflection on human conduct. Ethics aims to analyze, evaluate and develop normative moral criteria for dealing with moral principles. Ethics studies the reason why certain kinds of actions are morally right and commendable. The word “ethics” is used in three different but interwoven ways to mean a general pattern or way of life, to mean a set of rules of conduct or moral codes and thirdly to mean inquiry about ways of life and rules or conduct. Ethics deals with how we evaluate and justify actions which arise out of relationship as human beings.

Fágúnwà expressed Yorùbá ethical or moral values in his novel Àdìtù Olódùmarè through the use of Yorùbá folklores. He made use of these folklores to drive home the point that Yorùbá have a way of instilling good morals into their people by means of telling stories and through past experiences. These stories will be delved into in this paper to bring out the Yorùbá ethical values as expressed in Fágúnwà’s Àdìtù Olódùmarè.

Keywords: Moral, Ethics, Novel, Folklores, Rules of conduct.

INTRODUCTION.

Ethics, as a word, is derived from the Greek word “Ethos” meaning habit or custom. Ethics is the study of human conduct. It is a rational inquiry into the standards of right and wrong, good and in respect of character and conduct. Ethics studies the morality of human conduct and the basic principle of moral behavior. It deals basically with human being and how they ought to relate with others; both human and non-human in a bid to live a good life. According to Omoregbe, “Ethics like philosophy itself has no univocal definition. It can be defined as the branch of morality of human action; or as the branch of philosophy, which studies the norms of human behavior. Consequently, the justifications for certain actions are sought especially when we are in doubt as to human rightness or wrongness. In this regard, ethics can rightly be said to deal with how we evaluate and justify those actions which arise out of our relationship as human beings.

Having this issue of justification of human behavior in mind, the Yorùbá moral values as expressed in *Àdìtù Olódùmarè* will be discussed in this paper. The theory to be used for the work is Hermeneutics. Hermeneutics theory came to prominence with the work of Hans Geor Gadamer(1976) who says “the meaning of the text goes beyond the author and therefore the subject matter is what determines the meaning”. Hermeneutics tells us that we understand the whole of a text from its details. Etymologically, Hermeneutics is derived from the Greek verb generally translated as “to express”, “to explain” as in explaining a text. All these meanings are often expressed by the English verb “to interpret”. This in its broadest, general sense, Hermeneutics means interpretation. Madu says of Hermeneutics that “in its various ramifications, Hermeneutics suggests a process of bringing a thing or situation or text from unintelligibility to intelligibility”. In consonance with Madu’s definition, we are optimistic that the Hermeneutics theory will be resuscitative to materials from Yorùbá literary works by providing a deeper interpretation, especially of the Yorùbá ethical values as expressed in *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*. It is hoped that the Hermeneutics theory will facilitate a deeper understanding of the novel.

DISCUSSION

Ethics, is been defined as the study of moral behaviors. This moral can be a good or a bad one. In the novel *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*, the novelist told some stories that are morally oriented. Also, there are some scenes in the novel that the author used to pass some moral lessons to the readers. In this work, these stories will be highlighted to bring out the Yorùbá moral values.

As this novel, *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*, focuses on the protagonist, Àdìtù, It started with his family background. Àdìtù's parents Òbìrì-Ayé and Ìpónjùdìran used to be very rich in the earlier part of their life. But due to the recklessness of Òbìrì-Ayé, Àdìtù's father, things changed for the worse in their family. Òbìrì-Ayé was a great farmer, he was hard working and God blessed the work of his hands. When the farm yields started rolling in, Òbìrì-Ayé, as his name implied, turned another man entirely. He started to spend lavishly and have chains of concubines. As it is quoted below:

Nítorí èyí, inákuná ni ó n ná owó. Èyí tí ó wá burú ju gbogbo rẹ̀ lọ ni pé ó n gbé ẹ̀sẹ̀ ga ju. Èni tí ó n rí àádóta pónùn lódún n bá àwọn tí n gba àádóta pónùn lósù rìn irú ọ̀tí tí wọn n' mu ni ó n rà sílé, asọ tí wọn n lò ni òun náà n rà sọ̀rùn - - - ibi tí ó wá bá ohun gbogbo tí sí tí ó fi sọ ara rẹ̀ di tálákà gan an ni àwọn obìnrin ìkòkò tí ó tún n fẹ̀ kiri - - - [o.i.6]

Translated

Because of this, he spends money lavishly. The worst of it all is that he goes beyond his limits. Somebody that is getting fifty pounds in a year moving with the one that receives fifty pounds per month. He takes the same type of wine with them and buys the some clothes - - - The worst part of it that turned him to a pauper is the strange women that he goes after - - -

The author here expresses the reaction of the Yorùbá towards wasteful spending. It is a lesson in moral philosophy about wasteful spending. The Yorùbá have a serious hatred for somebody who is wasteful and who does not to have foresight. Òbìrì-Ayé had forgotten that he needed to plan for his future. Yorùbá people believe that any position one finds himself, he must not forget to plan for the future. That is the reason why the Yorùbá call a wasteful spender "Àpa" (prodigal) Amùṣà" (squanderer) to show that they are totally against such attitude.

Furthermore, the Yorùbá have a way of imparting knowledge into people. This is shown in their folktales which is part of their culture. This is a way of moral teaching whereby elders tell stories to the children or the younger ones to put them in the right way. This is also employed by Fágúnwà in the novel, *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*. After Àdìtù and Iyùn-adé's wedding, there was the post-wedding ceremony where people moved to Enúdùnjuyò's house to listen to stories from Mógàjí. As the name "Mógàjí" implies, it is the eldest person in the family that is called "Mogaji". According to Adéoyè (1979:261) the Mógàjí is being referred to as the "Baálè". He is the eldest in the family and the whole family is under him. Whatever he says is the final. Nobody dares go against his rules and regulations. That is the position that Fágúnwà put Mógàjí. In *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*, people gathered in Mógàjí's house to listen to stories that will teach them morals.

The first story is on reward for being good or bad. It was about a king named Òkònkò lójú abẹ. He had many wives out of which he had a favourite Èsan mbò. Other wives were envious of the favourite to the extent that the most senior wife, Ọmọ òwu planned to kill Èsan mbò. One day the king went on a journey and left the palace in care of the most senior wife. Ọmọ òwu planned for Èsan mbò, she drugged her to sleep and with the help of some of the servants in the palace, Èsan mbò was carried in a coffin and was taken to the boundary of the town where they use to bury the king's servants. Ọmọ òwu now carved a wood in place of Èsan mbò and buried it in the palace to deceive Òkònkò lójú abẹ, the king, that Èsan mbò was dead.

Meanwhile, Èsan mbò was loved by everybody in the palace. She was kind to the people around her. Some people in the palace knew about what Omọ òwu did to Èsan mbò. Fortunately for Èsan mbò, she was rescued by a merchant, Alábàápàdé, he took care of Èsan mbò and she was revived.

Later the king got to know about the truth of the matter when he heard the discussion of two women servants about the where about of Èsan mbò. Omọ òwu was severely punished for her actions and was driven out of the palace. As the name of Èsan mbò implies, Omọ òwu was rewarded for her bad behaviour but Èsan mbò, being a kind person met with Alábàápàdé who was kind to her, took care of her and made her to survive the ordeal she passed through. Alábàápàdé stood for the reward of good work that Èsan mbò had done in the past among the people in the palace. That was the reason why she got help in time of trouble. This shows that there is vengeance for whatever one does. God of vengeance visited Omọ òwu, the king's senior wife, who planned evil against Èsan mbò. She fell into the pit she dug for Èsan mbò. But Èsan mbò was elevated to a higher place. In the case of Alábàápàdé, he was not in a hurry to take what it was not his. This made him to receive the king's favour and mercy and he was rewarded for it.

- - - Alábàápàdé àti Èsan mbò fẹ ara wọn. Oba Òkònkò fún wọn ní owó reṣe, Alábàápàdé tún bèrèrè òwò síse, òwò n bí síí, ó n bí síí tó bèè tí ó fi jẹ pé iba diè ni oḅa pàápàá fi ní owó jù wọn lọ” [0.i.107]

Translated

Alábàápàdé and Èsan mbò got married. Òkò-ńkò the king gave them plenty of money. Alábàápàdé started his business and his riches increase to the extent that he was nearly richer than the king.

This is to show that the Yorùbá believe that one must be good, for whatsoever one sows he will reap. If one does well, goodness will follow one and vice versa. Another ethical issue in *Àdìtù Olódùmarè* by Mógàjí is the story of Kòtémilòrùn. The story was about a man who was too desperate to get rich. Despite the riches he inherited, he was not contented. He went ahead to make money rituals. Before he got involved in this ritual, Èsù warned him to desist from it, but he was adamant. He was given seven days to think over it. After this, Kòtémilòrùn decided to do the money rituals despite the condition given to him that he would have a number of years to live and to enjoy his riches. Also, he was told how his end would be and that he would spend his eternity in hell. This shows the extent of people's love for money. Money is good but too much love for money as recorded in 1 Timothy 6 verse 10 which says:

“for the love of money is the root of all evil” is not good

The love of money has put many into devilish things. Fágúnwà says

Àiní itélòrùn nípa owó ló wópò jù, kò sì sí nńkan tí àwọn ẹlòmíràn kò lè se láti rí owó - - - ọ̀pọ̀lọ̀pọ̀ ẹ̀nìyàn lóde ayé yí ni wọn ti n sọ ara wọn di yẹpẹrẹ nítorí owó, nítorí owó, wọn á sọ ara wọn di elékèé, òmíràn á ti ipá bèè kọ ipàkọ sí Olòrun oḅa” [0.i.109].

Translated

Discontentment of money is very common, People can do anything to have money - - - Many have rendered themselves useless because of money, they are not truthful and will turn against God.

At the end, Kòtémilòrùn died a painful death and went to hell to meet his punishment. This story shows the philosophical thought of the Yorùbá about excessive love for money. Avarice and covetousness make

people to look for money in a bad way. Yorùbá people believe that one should not be a slave to money and that one should not go out of his way to get money. They believe that too much of everything is bad. Wealth in Yorùbá philosophy is a good thing for it will give one the opportunity to take care of one's household; but looking for wealth in a bad way is what the Yorùbá frown at.

There is always a repercussion for discontentment. This can be seen in the life of Kòtémilòrùn. He ended his life in sorrow and pains. This was presented in his comments at the tail end of his life.

Ìgbà tí ó ,ku iséjú márùn-ún tí Kòtémilòrùn máa fi ayé silẹ̀, Èsù dé pèlu àwọn àngẹ̀lì rẹ̀ lati mú u lọ, òun nìkan ló rí wọn, Ìgbẹ̀ ńlá ni wọn kò gbó “A!, Èlẹ̀gbára, Èlẹ̀gbára, Èlẹ̀gbára, má fi agbára mú mi. A! O ha mí léèkán lójú! Nínú ojú! Léyinlójú! Ewó ni ti kùmò ní góngó imú? - - - [o.i.129]

Translated:-

When it remained five minutes for Kòtémilòrùn to die, the devil and his angels came to take him. He was the only one whosaw them. Those that were with him could not see them. They only heard a loud noise. “A! Èlẹ̀gbára, Èlẹ̀gbára, Èlẹ̀gbára don't take me by force. A! He pinched me at my eyeballs! Inside my eyeballs! A! What about hitting my nose with a cudgel - - - ?

Fágúnwà concluded this story by admonishing people on how not to treat money. He said:

Ká a tún sọ lèèkan sí i, owó níní dará, sùgbón kò yẹ kí èniyàn wá owó kojá ibi tí ó yẹ, Àwọn èlòmíràn wà lóde ayé tí wọn jẹ erú owó, kò só ohun tí wọn kò lè sè láti ríi. Òpòlopò tilẹ̀ se tó bèè tí ó jẹ pé á kó owó jọ lásán ni, áti lò ó fún ànfàání ara òun pàápàá di isòro, oúnjẹ wọn á burúju ti tálákà, asọ wón á pupa bí i ti àparò, ilé wọn kò sì dára ju búkà lọ síbẹ̀ owó wọn ló rẹbẹ̀tẹ̀ ní bànkì. Lójú tèmi, bí eni pé eni bèè ti gba èpè ló rí, irú àwọn wònyí pàápàá fẹ̀ràn owó ju ọmọ̀ lọ. Owó níní dára, sùgbón eni tí ó fi owó dípò Ọlòrun ọba, èsẹ̀ ńlá ni eléyíni gbàá”. [0.1.130]

Translated:

To repeat it again, wealth is good, but one should not exceed his limit in getting wealth. There are some people that are slaves to money, they can do anything to get rich. Some will even gather wealth but will not use it to their own benefit. They will eat bad food, their clothes will be dirty, their houses will be wretched, yet they have plenty of money in the bank. In my own view, it is like they are cursed. This type of people loves money than children. To acquire wealth is good, but whosoever replaces God with money has committed a great sin.

Another moral lesson that Fágúnwà illustrated in his novel is from the story of Òbédíní and Òbédèjì. The lesson that can be deduced from this story is the act of ingratitude. Òbédíní and Òbédèjì were brothers. Òbédíní was the elder brother to Òbédèjì. Òbédèjì rescued his brother from two incidents that would have claimed his life. The first one was about Ami, Òbédíní's wife, who was having an illicit affair with another man called Oníbàjé-Ọkùnrin. On two occasions, Oníbàjé-Ọkùnrin planned to get rid of Òbédíní so that he could take Ami as his wife. The first one was when Oníbàjé-Ọkùnrin was sending some men to go and set Òbédíní's house on fire so that he could be burnt inside. Òbédèjì got to know about this. He delivered his brother from this sudden death. The second incident was when Oníbàjé-Ọkùnrin dropped a corpse at Òbédíní's backyard. Òbédèjì spent money to bail him out and to employ a lawyer for him. Eventually, it was this same Òbédèjì that got a clue on how

Oníbàjé-Òkùnrin killed a man with his car and dropped the dead person at Òbédíní's backyard. Eventually when the truth was blown open, Òbédíní was released.

Afterwards, Òbédèjì got married to the king's daughter and by the virtue of his marriage to the king's daughter, he became rich. He gave money to his brother Òbédíní to run his business. There was a time, they both went on business trip. Òbédíní realized that Òbédèjì was more successful than him. This triggered envy in him. He became jealous of his brother to the extent that he colluded with his friend to kill his brother. So, on their journey, Òbédíní and his friend pushed Òbédèjì into the river for him to drown. But fortunately for Òbédèjì, he could swim; this was unknown to his brother. He now swam to the other side of the river. At the bank of the river, he met boxes full of gold and expensive materials. These made him richer. He went back home to become the king of his town after the demise of the former king who was his father-in-law.

When Òbédíní came back to the town, he was thinking that Òbédèjì had died. He went to the palace to report that it had been a long time he had parted with his brother during their business journey, only for him to meet Òbédèjì, his brother who had become the king. He was ashamed of himself when he saw his brother being the king. Òbédèjì ordered Òbédíní to be thrown into the sea.

What Fágúnwà is pointing out here is the enigma of life in Yorùbá philosophy. The Yorùbá believe that it is devilish to pay good with evil. That is why they frown at the act of ingratitude. From the story above, what can be deduced is that whatever one does for an ingrate, he will never appreciate it. Despite all Òbédèjì did for Òbédíní to save his life and to make him live comfortably, yet he was not satisfied. He still planned to kill Òbédèjì. He bit the finger that fed him.

As for Òbédèjì, he trusted his brother Òbédíní so much to the extent that he would not look back in doing him any good. Fágúnwà made it clear about the belief of the Yorùbá that good people always believe that everybody is like them. So, they don't think twice before they do good things. This was expressed when he said:

Òbédèjì jẹbi tí púpọ̀ nínú àwọn èniyàn rere máa ń jẹ, òun ni pé wọn máa ń gbékẹlẹ̀ èniyàn jù. Wọn máa ń rò pé kò sòro fún ẹnikan láti hùwà rere, nítorí èyí, Òbédèjì kò funra sí ẹgbọn rẹ rára kò sì fi ohunkóhun pamọ̀ fún un".
[0.1.141]

Translated:-

Òbédèjì is also guilty of what most good people are guilty of, which is, they trust other people too much. They always think it is not difficult to behave well. For this reason, Òbédèjì did not suspect his brother and he did not hide anything for him.

Òbédèjì was highly disappointed at Òbédíní's behaviour. He did not expect that Òbédíní could hurt him talk less of killing him. This made him to say:

Òbédíní, Òbédíní , Ha! Òbédíní! O ti fi ojú idà idílẹ̀ gbo'lẹ̀ o ba ẹbí jẹ, o ti tàpá sí ẹgún o bá Ọlórún wọ jàkadì. O kọ ẹyìn sí Olódùmarè tí ó dá ọ. Òbédíní, níbo ni ẹrì ọkàn rẹ wà, nígbà tí o ń gbé esè mi, tí o ń gbé apá mi, tí o ń gbimò pẹlú ẹnikẹjì tí ẹ jù mí sínú omi ọkun? Òbédíní, òjẹ ẹmí rẹ ibá wà lóní, láì sí mí? N jẹ iwo ibá máa rí owó s'ówó láì sí mí? [1.0.143]

Translated:

Òbédiní, Òbédiní, Ha! Òbédiní! You have betrayed the family ties, You destroyed the family, you have gone against the family bond. You wrestle with God, you turned against the Almighty that created you. Òbédiní, where is your conscience when you were carrying my legs, carrying my hands, colluding with your friend, dropping me into the sea? Òbédiní, would you have been alive without me? Would you have gotten money for business without me?

Another incident in *Àdìtù Olódùmarè* as narrated by Fágúnwà to show the Yorùbá philosophical thought about bad and deceitful friends and their end is portrayed in the story of Èsù léyìn ibejì. Èsù léyìn ibejì was a close friend to Àdìtù. He was so close to Àdìtù to the extent that he was in charge of Àdìtù's business when he was away. Despite this closeness, Èsù léyìn ibejì planned for destruction of Àdìtù and Iyùn-adé's relationship. He wrote a letter to Iyùn-adé [as recorded in *Àdìtù* [pg: 87-88] telling her lies about Àdìtù. He did the same thing to Àdìtù. He wrote another letter to Àdìtù telling him that Iyùn-adé was promiscuous. If not for the understanding between Àdìtù and Iyùn-adé, Èsù léyìn ibejì would have scattered their relationship. He did not stop at that, he wanted to have illicit affair with one of the princes' wives. The wife informed her husband and a trap was set for Èsù léyìn ibejì. He was caught in his attempt to sleep with the woman. Also, he personally killed his own brother thinking that he had killed Àdìtù. Èsù léyìn ibejì dearly paid for his betrayal attitude by losing his life and his brother. He died a painful and gradual death.

The philosophical implication of the Yorùbá about keeping friends is illustrated in this story. This brings about a Yorùbá adage that says:-

“Èni a fẹ la mò, a ò mẹnì tó fẹni”

“(You only know who you love and not who loves you].

Not all that appears as friends are true friend. This shows that not all human beings are reliable. There are people that appear as friends but deep inside them they are devil. The unscrupulous behaviour of Èsù léyìn ibejì shows that not all that glitters is gold. Also, it shows that one should think over any piece of advice given by people before taking to it. It is not every advice that is truthful or useful, One needs to look before leaping. You don't leap at everything you hear from people. You need to sieve the good from the bad. This is so because: - “Ojú la rí, òrẹ ò dénú” [People are hypocrites].

CONCLUSION.

In this paper, we have tried to bring out the Yorùbá moral values as expressed in the novel *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*. The Yorùbá hold in high esteem anyone that is morally upright, that is why they always frown at anybody that misbehaves or that puts up bad behavior. They make use of their folklores to preach good moral and to castigate anybody found wanting. Such folklores are highlighted in the novel, *Àdìtù Olódùmarè*.

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